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CULTURAL ASPECT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES TEACHING FOR HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS STUDENTS

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The aim of the study is to examine cultural aspect of foreign languages teaching for higher educational establishment's students and analyze new approaches of its organizing in contemporary theory and practice as well as to study and emphasize its cultural features and mechanisms. Methods of research include critical analyses of literature on the subject of research, containing a retrospective study of home and foreign experience, which allows to summarize and to formulate the basic teaching methods taking into account cultural approach. The scientific novelty consists of a comprehensive consideration of peculiarities of foreign languages culture process learning through foreign language.

Conclusions. It has been proved that one of the main objectives of foreign language teaching is social-cultural development of learners' personality. And cultural approach in foreign language teaching prepare them to intercultural communication, that in its turn means acquaintance of students with culture of the countries of the target language, promotes students' formation of respect for other cultures and peoples, readiness to business cooperation and mutual support, joint solving of universal problems.

Keywords: cultural aspect; culture; foreign language; foreign language teaching; intercultural communication; social-cultural competence.

Introduction

The development of business and personal contacts, broadening and strengthening of economic and cultural ties among people put to the forefront in the field of foreign languages learning a task to educate a person, for whom an important asset is universal culture and human values. This task is directly related to the problem of understanding between people, their spiritual connection and common ways of progress making.

One solution of this issue is the humanization of education i.e. students' initiation to the cultural heritage and spiritual values of native people and others peoples of the world. A special role in this process belongs to foreign language, with the help of which direct and indirect dialogue of cultures is implemented, that is one of the main concepts of modern education.

Humanization of education content requires a revision of objectives, contents and techniques of foreign languages learning as new means of

communication – new way of intercultural communication and cross-cultural understanding. As the purpose of foreign languages learning is not just knowledge acquiring, formation of students' abilities and skills, but also their information assimilation of Country studies, lingual, cultural and aesthetic nature, knowledge of other national culture, in determining of education contest the question of cultural component obviously raises.

Theoretical importance of the work consists of the comprehensive consideration of features of the foreign language culture learning process through a foreign language.

Recently in the scientific psycho-pedagogical literature education is increasingly seen as an integrated system based on the values of culture. The analyses of pedagogical researches and practical observations indicate growing interest to the problem of education and necessity of universal human moral values strengthening. Cultural approach to education has developed in the scientific works of L. White, E. Sepir, N. Trubetskaya, V. Sidorienko, A. Zapesotskiy; cultural approach in foreign languages training was also covered by E. Vereshchagin, V. Rostomarov, L. Blumfeld, V. Maslova, V. Safonova, M. Suvorova, V. Khrolenko, V. Furmanova, V. Teliya (Safonova, 2011, p. 79) The great contribution to the research of foreign languages training process in the field of Philology was made by S. Ter-Minasova, O. Leontovych, N. Troshyna, in Ethnopsihology – A. Stefanenko, N. Liebiedieva, V. Sadohin, V. Krysko. With cultural approach to education not only fundamental and applied knowledge are essential, but the principles, which are relevant to professional culture, the ethics of the attitude to work and professional interaction, traditions, attributes of prestige and other role signs of a specialists in the area i.e. full integration in social functional stratum (professional cultural society) of specialists as well as in work. The aim of the article is to examine the peculiarities of foreign culture teaching with means of foreign language in high education institution conditions.

The purpose of the article

The purpose of the study is a foreign languages studying in higher education institutions in consideration with cultural aspect.

Achieving this goal involves solving the following tasks: to examine educational and methodical literature on this issue; to define the essence of foreign languages culture, as a component of foreign language training content; to describe the cultural aspect in foreign languages teaching; to consider the basic ways of foreign languages culture learning through a foreign language.

The object of the research study is a foreign languages culture in the process of foreign languages teaching in higher education establishments.

The subject of the study is foreign language teaching in consideration of cultural aspect.

Pedagogical attention to cultural problems of education is steadily growing nowadays. It became as a result of various traditions' consideration of culture and education of different countries interaction. In modern theory and practice

of education it is observed a tendency not only to the new approaches of its organization searching but also a new, special and adequate to modern culture and science understanding of cultural specificities and mechanisms. “Foreign language” is an academic discipline, which not only introduces the culture of other countries using comparison emphasizes the features of its native country, introduces the values common to all mankind, i.e. promote the students’ education in “the dialogue of two cultures” context. The implementation of cultural components in foreign language teaching is necessary for the main practical goal achievement: that is formation an ability to communicate in foreign language. This fact causes the relevance of the chosen research topic.

Presentation of the main material

Language is a gift, which extends the abilities of a person, his or her mindset, perception, memory and imagination. We speak the language in which we speak and every language reflects the same reality differently. So it should be accurate, in order we can understand each other, flexible to allow the words acquire new nuances of meaning. Mastering a foreign language we expand our horizon of knowledge, sink into another language environment, enrich our vocabulary, develop our memory and improve mental abilities. It leads to better integration in foreign language environment and adaptation to its condition. High school task is to create conditions for the creating and development of students’ professional skills. Specially created components of the educational process and purposefully organized space of professional competence formation contribute to the development of the students’ need for joint activity, working out a strategy of interaction, certain knowledge mastering, skills and abilities. The relationship of foreign languages learning and intercultural communication is obvious. In the sphere of foreign languages great changes are taking place caused by the enormous interest to it. Unprecedented demand has spawned the need for relevant proposals. The specialists from different areas required an immediate learning of foreign language as a tool of professional work and real communication with people of other countries. New time dictates the tendency to review the general methods and techniques of teaching immediately. In high educational establishment the learning of foreign language as a means of communication with specialists of different countries is not considered as applied and highly specialized task. Modern specialist is an intelligent person with fundamental skills. Foreign language for such specialist is a tool of highly professional work performing and a part of culture. The foreign language communicative competence is the main task of modern specialists (Kostenko, 2012, pp. 86 –89).

Today culture is understood as a generalized civilized space i.e. as a product of human thought and activity. Therefore, culture includes the experience and rules governing and regulating human life, attitudes of people to new and various things. Consequently, in the foreign language teaching process, which has strong intercultural dominant, the value aspect should be reflected as well as factual and country studies aspects. Thus, intercultural component dictates

the need for search of new psychological-pedagogical and methodological solutions aimed at formation of students' intercultural communicative culture and "extension" of educational process frameworks through entrance of students into real intercultural communicational context. Implementation of cultural approach gives an opportunity to rethink the specificity of foreign language.

Central problems of teaching techniques are determining the goals as well as adequate them content of training, in which the ideas not only languages studying but foreign language culture learning in wide sense of the word are considered as the most effective.

Foreign language teaching system under cultural approach includes the complex of (Suvorov, 2007):

- goals, content, methods, means, process of learning activity and interaction of teacher and students;
- the autonomous activities of trainees (exercises);
- education control;
- social-cultural background of educational environment due to the society's order for specialists training.

The following components of foreign language teaching can be specified (Furmanova, 2013, p. 90):

- communicative situations, reflecting the everyday household needs;
- situations of contact personal communication;
- situations of social-political nature;
- situations of professional communication.

Cultural approach envisages that foreign language teaching must meet the principles of complementarities, the correlation education activity's components on the base of connection of professional language training with individual needs and value orientations of students.

According to theoretical analyses the implementation of cultural approach in foreign languages teaching creates the condition, which is aimed first of all at the general common cultural training through the deepening of the study in the context of specific knowledge area, which is relevant to professionalization (Strelchuk, 2011, pp. (276–278).

Cultural approach must perform five functions: developing, training, educational, informative and professional.

Developing function. Its essence is that foreign language culture is aimed at the development of the socially and professionally significant features of a student's personality, which play the most important role in the process of cognition, namely

- mental functions related to speech activity (speech thinking, attention, memory in all its forms, imagination, perception, etc.);
- speech abilities (phonemic hearing, sense of language, ability to guess, discern, imitation, logical presentation, etc.);
- such traits of character as hardworking, sense of purpose, volition, activity;
- learning skills.

Training function. Cultural approach implies possession of all speech functions and different forms of communication with the objective that mastering of professional foreign language culture can be means of enriching the spiritual world of students, interpersonal and intercultural communication, asserting their belief, promoting intercultural partnership and social progress, native culture etc. Every type of speech activity has its own specific objectives: speaking, listening, two-way translation (from native language into foreign one and vice-versa), reading and writing.

Educational function is that foreign language culture is a means of moral education. The following features exist in order to implement moral education in professional foreign language communication:

- informative (various issues);
- organizational (discussing this issues and their interpretation).

Cognitive function. Mastering of foreign language culture is aimed to understand this culture but not just learn its content, because it's impossible to comprehend the whole culture of the country in full even in the process of foreign language learning. It's necessary to remember that every nation has its mentality, which is strikingly different from others. Mentality understanding is possible only through mastering of culture. People coming into intercultural professional communication must understand that understanding in intercultural dialogue is achieved through the acquaintance to foreign language culture, respecting and recognition of its self-worth. Mastering the culture is the comprehension of people's value system (Donets, 2001, p. 384).

Professional function. Its essence is that foreign language culture determines the professional specificity inherent to any people. Staying in foreign country can cause various emotions. A person coming abroad might admire another reality: buildings, shops, food and style of clothing. However, a specialist arrived in the foreign country, started to work feels an influence of foreign culture on his or her life. The unfamiliarity with etiquette and foreign culture can lead to cultural shock, which manifests itself in avoiding contacts with the representatives of foreign language culture, fatigue, nervousness, anxiety. The confidence in foreign language communication can be obtained only in the process of practice.

Recent researches suggest that the study of language communication in the light of social linguistics is relevant nowadays and begin to acquire more pragmatic character. The social experience of people primarily reflects in language. The existence of different lexical units is determined by practical needs of people, their life realities.

The developing reserves of foreign language as a means of cultural competence of students forming most comprehensively reveal themselves if:

- a student becomes not object but subject of training activity;
- students themselves put meaningful for them aims and the situation of successes created on the lessons help them to reach targets.
- students complete assignments, which have clear, personal meaning;
- creative tasks simulate various aspects of human activity;
- equal communicative interaction with a teacher is carried out.

To implement lingual cultural approach in foreign language teaching the principles of culture conformity and developing education are the central.

It can be achieved by the following methods:

- encouraging and stimulating of students' interests;
- encouraging of creativity;
- method of problem issues and situations;
- partially searching and researching methods;
- content-analysis and lingual cultural analysis of proverbs, sayings, phrase logical units and specific English sayings, authentic materials (Gilmore, 2007);
- method of mastering all aspects of the language through the prism of culture;
- method of accustoming, designed to develop the skills of cultural behavior:
- natural method in teaching English.

Therefore, it's necessary to pay great attention to proverbs, sayings and idioms, emphasizing their various meanings, which representatives of different cultures put into the same words as well as using varying phrases. When learning language and foreign language culture, particular attention should be paid to the authenticity and value relevance of foreign language materials used for forming students' perceptions of contemporary multicultural and multilingual world, universal human and national values, the cultural heritage of native and foreign countries (Nosovich, Milrud, 2009, pp. 11–18). It is not acceptable to use foreign language materials, which could form among students misperceptions about the history and culture of foreign countries and Ukraine. The material used in the educational process should meet the age characteristics, cognitive and communication abilities of students at each stage of teaching.

For the most complete immersion into the culture of the language learned, it is necessary to familiarize students with the cultural background, which stands for language units and helps to correlate superficial structures with their essence (Chunyan Sun, 2015, pp. 7–9).

Talking about modern approaches in teaching the researching method of learning can be mentioned. The method of research is a learning process when students are placed in position, in which they choose themselves the way of problem solving, possessing the concepts and approaches to solve the problem organized by the teacher. In the approach the problems connected with the students' experience and their life needs and interests are relevant (Lier, 2001, pp. 166–172).

We can distinguish three levels research implementation:

- The teacher puts the problem and outlines the strategy and tactics of its solving;
- The teacher raises a problem, the method of its solving is searched by students themselves (collective search is permitted);
- The student themselves raise the problem, look for the ways of researching and work out the solution.

The usage of modern information technologies provides an opportunity to learn life experience with a means of foreign language in real information space (Voronina, 2009, p.36).

Objectively existing information environment contains the following areas:

- Books (fiction, educational books, guide books, scientific literature)
- Periodicals;
- Radio and television;
- Multimedia and software means, including educational and training tools;
- Global and local networks of educational purpose;
- Using of Internet for educational aims is a reality nowadays.

Audiovisual language environment contributes to creating conditions for language assimilation in the contact with culture. We can also use the Internet as a tool for teaching, learning, information getting and communication. Proper using of computer telecommunications, information recourses and internet services allows to implement fundamentally new approach to foreign language training. It's based on wide communication, convergence, erasing the boundaries between societies, free exchange of ideas and information, initiates wide contacts with the culture and experience of other peoples, stimulates foreign language mastering, if we are talking about international projects.

Participation in various telecommunication projects, conferences, an ability to link with different libraries of the world expand the world of a student, bring a lot of information in the life and mostly in English.

Such technologies as communicative, role, situational, linguistically oriented activity as well as methods of projects are used in learning process and give the teacher an opportunity to put the students in real communication full of foreign language contacts, based on research activity, joint work and to see the real results of the work.

Conclusions

Based on foregoing, it can be argued that foreign language culture is complicated and multifaceted concept and it's unlikely that it can be studied by students to the full. Therefore we believe that for language training of competitive specialist it's necessary to choose selecting principles of foreign language culture required and sufficient for entering foreign culture, which allow managing this process. That's why this study requires further researching and continuous improvement. Modern living conditions require learning a foreign language, especially its functionality. Now people not only want to know the language but use it as a means of real communication with speakers of other cultures. Increasing demand for a foreign languages teaching in turn dictates its own terms.

It is required to know the culture of the target language as thoroughly as possible. Theoretical knowledge should be complemented by practical skills of communication in different contexts. That's why now more attention is paid to the world of language i.e. learning the country in which the learning language is spoken.

Learning of cultural component of words is an important condition in foreign language successful mastering and is included in a wider range of cultural and historical values of corresponding social reality, knowing of which is an important term of foreign language using as a means of communication.

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КУЛЬТУРОЛОГІЧНИЙ АСПЕКТ ВИКЛАДАННЯ ІНОЗЕМНОЇ МОВИ СТУДЕНТАМ ЗАКЛАДІВ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Мета статті. Дослідити культурологічний аспект викладання іноземної мови студентам закладів вищої освіти та проаналізувати нові підходи для його організації в сучасній теорії та практиці. Методологія дослідження базується на критичному аналізі літературних джерел з теми дослідження, зокрема ретроспективне вивчення вітчизняного та закордонного досвіду, що дозволяє узагальнити та сформулювати основні методи викладання іноземної мови з урахуванням культурологічного підходу. Наукова новизна полягає у комплексній систематизації процесу навчання іношомовній культурі через іноземну мову.

Висновки. Доведено, що однією з основних цілей навчання іноземній мові є соціокультурний розвиток особистості студентів. А культурологічний підхід у викладанні іноземної мови залучає їх до міжкультурного спілкування, насамперед, передбачає ознайомлення з культурою країни, мова якої вивчається, сприяє формуванню у студентів поваги до інших культур та народів, готовності до ділової співпраці та взаєморозумінню, спільному вирішенню загальнолюдських проблем.

Ключові слова: культурологічний аспект; культура; іноземна мова; викладання іноземної мови; міжкультурна комунікація; соціокультурна компетенція.

КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АСПЕКТ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА СТУДЕНТАМ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ

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Цель статьи. Исследовать культурологический аспект преподавания иностранного языка студентам высших учебных заведений и проанализировать новые подходы в его организации в современной теории и практике. Методология исследования включает критический анализ литературных источников по теме исследования, в том числе ретроспективное изучение отечественного и зарубежного опыта, позволяющего обобщить и сформулировать основные методы преподавания иностранного языка с учётом культурологического подхода. Научная новизна заключается в комплексной систематизации процесса обучения иноязычной культуре

через иностранный язык. Выводы. Доказано, что одной из основных целей обучения иностранному языку является социокультурное развитие личности обучаемых. А культурологический подход в преподавании иностранного языка готовит их к межкультурному общению, что в свою очередь предполагает ознакомление с культурой стран изучаемого языка, способствует формированию у студентов уважения к другим культурам и народам, готовности к деловому сотрудничеству и взаимопомощи, совместному решению общечеловеческих проблем.

Ключевые слова: культурологический аспект; культура; иностранный язык; преподавание иностранного языка; межкультурная коммуникация; социокультурная компетенция.